

Popular Article

Autogenous Ascites Fluid Reinfusion Therapy In Dog

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Abstract

Ascites in dog is a common complication of the hepatorenal syndrome which is usually due to portal hypertension and hypalbuminemia. Hypalbuminemia causes reduced oncotic pressure and portal hypertension leads to retention of sodium and water, which cause accumulation of fluid in peritoneal cavity. A dog presented with ascites was reinfused with autogenous ascites fluid and supportive treatment was given. This therapy proved effective in treatment of ascites.

Introduction

Ascites is a pathological accumulation of free fluids within the peritoneal cavity (Edward J. Hall, 2005). Ascites is a reflection of one, or a combination of different, pathophysiological mechanisms (Edward J. Hall, 2005) and is usually reserved for a transudate that results from liver or right-side heart failure. Ascites in animals with liver disease is usually due to portal hypertension, although in some cases hypalbuminaemia may contribute to its pathogenesis (Bexfield and Watson, 2009).

Reduced oncotic pressure due to hypoalbuminemia occurring as a result of protein losing enteropathy (PLE), protein losing nephropathy (PLN), liver failure (chronic hepatitis/cirrhosis) and increased hydrostatic pressure due to portal hypertension, hepatic vein occlusion, congestive heart failure can cause fluid accumulation in the abdomen (*Haridas Vijayakumar et al,2013*).

Ascites association with portal hypotension is aggravated by alteration in renal sodium handling and systemic conservation of water. Initial derangement occurs with imbalance of transcapillary fluid fluxes in the hepatic sinusoids and splanchnic lymphatics. This results in excessive lymph formation that exceeds the capacity of the lymphatics and thoracic duct. Excess lymph accumulates in the peritoneal cavity and subsequent, causes a contraction of the circulating plasma volume. As ascites accumulates, there is gradual redistribution of plasma volume, resulting in reduction of the effective circulating plasma volume. A reduction in effective intravascular volume invokes renal conservation of sodium (antinatriuresis) and water (antidiuretic hormone). This sodium retention leads to plasma volume expansion, which, in the setting of abnormal Starling force (portal hypertension, reduced plasma oncotic pressure) in the sinusoids and splanchnic circulation, promotes ascites formation.

History and clinical observation

A two-year male dog weighing 37 kg with a history of abdominal distension, normal appetite, normal mucous membrane, was brought to veterinary clinical complex, Bihar Veterinary College, Patna. Fluid thrill during tactile percussion was felt. The dog was subjected to biochemical and radiographic examination. Radiographic examination of abdomen revealed ground glass appearance and biochemical examination showed hypoalbuminemia and hypoproteinaemia. Remaining parameter was within normal range. Based on radiographic and biochemical examination the case was diagnosed as ascites

Figure 1: X-ray of abdomen showing ground glass appearance indicating free fluid in peritoneal cavity

Table-1 Serum biochemical profile of Ascites dog (Before and after therapy)

Parameters	Day-0	Day 21	Reference range*
SGPT/ALT(U/lit)	21.3	28.7	10-109
SGOT/AST(U/lit)	24.7	42.4	13-15
Albumin(g/dl)	1.41	3.57	2.3-04
Total protein(g/dl)	4.06	5.64	5.4-7.5
Urea nitrogen(mg/dl)	24.78	21.59	08-28
Creatinine(mg/dl)	0.86	0.87	0.5-1.5

*The Mercks Veterinary Manual, 11th edition

Therapeutic procedure and discussion

Diagnostic abdominal paracentesis (Beal, 2005) was done and ascitic fluid was collected following all aseptic condition. Fresh 60 ml of ascites fluid was collected, centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 min and 40 ml of ascites fluid was infused intravenously into the same dog once. Supportive treatment with furosemide(2mg/kg), silimarin, antibiotics (ceftriaxone and tazobactam @ 10mg/kg) was given. Owner was advised to restrict sodium in the diet and feed high protein diet.

After 21 days there was considerable recovery and reduction in peritoneal fluid. Ascites is a pathological accumulation of fluid in peritoneal cavity which is a common complication of hepatorenal syndrome which is usually due to portal hypertension and hypalbuminaemia. Prompt diagnosis and Autogenous ascites fluid therapy can be an effective and economical way to treat ascites in dogs.

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